

Mg²⁺ and is in agreement with the Maley and Mellor order⁵.

Fig. 2. Metal-ligand systems of 5-methyl-salicylidene-p-nitro-aniline.

TABLE I—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES*

Cations	$t=25^\circ$				
	H ⁺	Cu ²⁺	Ni ²⁺	Co ²⁺	Mg ²⁺
log K ₁	10.90	8.7	6.6	5.88	4.17
log K ₂	—	6.66	—	—	—

* For proton association (H⁺), K₁ correspond to the species LH, while for metal ions K₁ and K₂ correspond to the species ML₁ and ML₂ respectively.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to record their sincere thanks to Dr. D. G. Vartak, B.A.R.C., Bombay, for his valuable suggestions and to Prof. A.P. Rao, Vice-Principal, Ramnarain Ruia College, Bombay, for his kind and continuous encouragement in accomplishing this work.

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Studies on Th(IV) and Zr(IV) Complexes of Oxygen Donor Ligands-V. Oxozirconium(IV) Complexes of Pyridine N-Oxide and 2,6-Lutidine N-Oxide†

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Manuscript received 12 April 1979, revised 13 November 1980, accepted 28 January 1981

RECENTLY a large number of coordination compounds of pyridine N-oxide and its ring substituted derivatives with a wide variety of metal salts have been synthesised and characterised¹⁻³. Comparatively very little is known about the compounds of oxozirconium(IV) with aromatic amine N-oxides⁴⁻⁸. In this communication we describe some hitherto unknown complexes of pyridine N-oxide (PyO) and 2,6-lutidine N-oxide (LNO) with oxozirconium(IV) salts.

Experimental

ZrO(NO₃)₂·5H₂O and ZrOCl₂·4H₂O were obtained from BDH. Anhydrous ZrOCl₂ was prepared as reported earlier⁹. Crystalline zirconyl perchlorate was prepared by established method¹⁰. Other zirconyl halides were prepared from chloride salt. Pyridine N-oxide was prepared by the method of Ochiai¹¹, while 2,6-lutidine N-oxide was obtained from Aldrich Chemical Company Inc., U.S.A. Crystalline adducts were isolated by one of the following methods :

(a) In a typical experiment ethanolic solution of Lewis acid was mixed with slight excess of ligand. The reaction mixture was concentrated on a water bath. The concentrated mass was cooled to which an excess amount of diethyl ether was added—an oily viscous layer was obtained. This viscous layer was separated and washed thoroughly with ether. The viscous mass was dissolved in the minimum amount of absolute ethanol and again an excess of diethyl ether was added and a precipitate was obtained. It was filtered, washed with small amount of ethanol and ether, dried in vacuo over anhydrous CaCl₂.

(b) A solution of Lewis acid in ethanol was treated with an excess of the Lewis base in the same solvent. The mixture was refluxed ca. 3h and the excess solvent was removed by distillation. The

† Presented at the 48th Annual Session of National Academy of Sciences (India), Gauhati University, Gauhati, on Oct. 22-24, 1978.

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, CONDUCTIVITY, MOLECULAR WEIGHT DATA, DECOMPOSITION TEMPERATURE AND IR ABSORPTION FREQUENCIES FOR OXOZIRCONIUM(IV) COMPLEXES OF PYO AND LNO

Compound	Method of preparation	Colour	Metal % Found (Calc)	Nitrogen % Found (Calc)	Anion % Found (Calc)	λ_m ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹	Electrolytic nature	Mol. wt. Found (Calc)	DTA decomposition temp. (°C)	$\nu(\text{NO})$ cm ⁻¹	$\nu(\text{M-O})$ cm ⁻¹ metal ligand stretching
ZrO(PyO) ₂ (NO ₂) ₂	a	Light yellow	21.57 (21.61)	13.41 (13.30)	—	4.7 ^a 9.8 ^b	Non electrolyte	401 (421)	270	1210s	400m
ZrO(PyO) ₂ Cl ₂	c	White	24.91 (24.72)	7.49 (7.60)	19.10 (19.29)	4.9 ^a 9.6 ^b	Non electrolyte	320 (368)	265	1210s	400m
ZrO(PyO) ₂ Br ₂	a	Light yellow	20.06 (19.91)	6.06 (6.10)	35.36 (35.01)	4.8 ^a 11.7 ^b	Non electrolyte	427 (457)	260	1230s	390m
ZrO(PyO) ₂ I ₂	a	Yellow	12.39 (12.28)	7.42 (7.55)	33.82 (34.27)	48.3 ^a 78.7 ^b	1 : 2 electrolyte	220 (741)	180	1212s	390m
ZrO(PyO) ₂ (NOS) ₂	a	White pink	22.10 (22.03)	13.50 (13.55)	27.91 (28.08)	4.1 ^a 10.9 ^b	Non electrolyte	398 (413)	250	1215s	400m
ZrO(LNO) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂	b	Light brown	8.89 (8.71)	8.01 (8.04)	18.67 (19.06)	50.7 ^a 79.7 ^b	1 : 2	309 (1044)	305	1220s	370m
ZrO(LNO) ₂ (NO ₂) ₂	a	Light yellow	18.93 (19.07)	11.87 (11.74)	—	4.6 ^a 9.3 ^b	Non electrolyte	430 (477)	270	1218s	375m
ZrO(LNO) ₂ Cl ₂	c	White	21.30 (21.46)	6.52 (6.60)	16.42 (16.74)	4.2 ^a 10.6 ^b	Non electrolyte	406 (424)	260	1210s	375m
ZrO(LNO) ₂ Br ₂	a	White	17.91 (17.73)	5.61 (5.45)	30.83 (31.18)	4.3 ^a 8.9 ^b	Non electrolyte	490 (513)	260	1220s	365m
ZrO(LNO) ₂ I ₂	a	Yellow	10.75 (10.66)	6.49 (6.56)	28.91 (29.77)	48.7 ^a 78.3 ^b	1 : 2 electrolyte	270 (859)	160	1222s	360m
ZrO(LNO) ₂ (NOS) ₂	a	White pink	19.58 (19.40)	12.01 (11.94)	24.29 (24.73)	3.9 ^a 9.7 ^b	Non electrolyte	429 (469)	250	1222s	362m

^a—In nitrobenzene; ^b—In dimethyl sulphoxide.

residual mass on treatment with diethyl ether yielded a crystalline solid which was filtered, washed with diethyl ether and dried in vacuo.

(c) A solution of Lewis acid in ethanol was treated with an excess of Lewis base in the same solvent. The mixture was refluxed ca. 3h. After cooling the reaction mixture, a solid mass settled. It was filtered, washed with ethanol and ether and dried.

The analyses and physical measurements of the complexes were made as reported previously^{12,13}.

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometries of the isolated compounds have been established on the basis of elemental analyses (Table 1). The compounds are sufficiently soluble in polar solvents and insoluble in non-polar solvents. The electrical conductance measurement in nitrobenzene and dimethyl sulphoxide indicate (Table 1) that the chloro, bromo, nitrate and thiocyanato complexes are non-electrolytes while the iodo and perchlorato complexes are 1 : 2 electrolytes. The molecular weight determination of the complexes also supported the same electrolytic nature of the complexes.

The differential thermal behaviour of the complexes studied and the decomposition temperatures are provided in Table 1. In dta curves no peak around 100° has been observed indicating that the complexes are not hygroscopic in nature and stable

at that temperature. The chloro, bromo and nitrate complexes decompose endothermically while perchlorato and thiocyanato complexes decompose exothermically, the former decomposing violently due to the oxygen content of the perchlorate. On decomposition, all the complexes produce carbon and metal. A broad exotherm around 470° is due to the oxidation of carbon. A final exothermic peak below 700° in all the complexes is due to the metal oxidation.

In the ir spectra of free PyO and LNO, the NO stretching vibration appears as a strong band at ~1265 cm⁻¹ and ~1245 cm⁻¹ studied here, the NO stretching vibration mode suffers a significant negative shift ($-\Delta\nu$ NO = 25-55 cm⁻¹). The decrease in the frequency of the NO stretching vibration is attributed to coordination from the oxygen atom of the base causing a decrease in π -character of the N-O bond^{16,17}. The NO bending vibration of the pyridine N-oxide and its derivatives has been assigned as a strong band^{14,15} at ~840 cm⁻¹. It is apparent that only a slight shift of this vibration is observed on complexation^{17,18}, which may be due to two opposing effects, one similar to that of coordinated water, where the bending vibration $\delta(\text{OH})$ is shifted to the higher frequency and the other attributed to lowering in frequency caused by the decrease in π character of the NO bond. As the quantum of both these effects is practically equal, a very small shift in the frequency is observed in the spectra of the oxozirconium(IV) complexes of these ligands. Absorptions associated with C-H out-of-plane deformation modes in PyO at ~758 cm⁻¹ and in LNO at ~762 cm⁻¹, are supposed to

undergo slight positive shift due to tightening of the aromatic ring on complexation. A positive shift of $\sim 15 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ has been observed in this mode of vibration which is in conformity with the observations of earlier workers^{1,6,17}.

The Zr=O double bond characteristic stretching frequency have been observed in all the complexes at $\sim 960 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ modes have been assigned in the range $400\text{-}350 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ^{6,12,18}

In $\text{ZrO}(\text{LNO})_6(\text{ClO}_4)_2$, the very strong ν_3 band and a strong ν_4 band have appeared at $\sim 1082 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 620 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively, for the perchlorate ion, indicating that the tetrahedral symmetry is maintained and the perchlorate ions are not bonded to the zirconium ion^{6,20}. In the thiocyanato complexes $\nu(\text{CN})$, $\nu(\text{CS})$ and $\delta(\text{NCS})$ frequencies observed at ~ 2045 , ~ 785 and $\sim 490 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively, support the N-bonding isothiocyanate ion²¹. The absence of the ν_3 band of ionic nitrate (D_{3h}) around $\sim 1360 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the occurrence of two strong bands at $\sim 1525 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 1300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in spectra of nitrate complexes of PyO and LNO suggest the coordination of nitrate in these complexes^{22,23}. The bidentate nature of nitrate groups are confirmed by the presence of bands at $\sim 1030 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ν_2), 800 cm^{-1} (ν_6) and 730 cm^{-1} (ν_3/ν_5).

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (R.K.A.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for the award of a teacher fellowship.

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On the "Solvates" of Metal Acetates with Acetic Anhydride

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Manuscript received 24 January 1979, revised 26 September 1980, accepted 28 January 1981

THE products obtained by a slow reaction of alkali acetates (M^+OAc^-) with acetic anhydride (Ac_2O) have been termed¹ as "solvates" (complexes) of M^+OAc^- with Ac_2O . We find² that the product of the Perkin reaction of PhCHO , Ac_2O and K^+OAc^- contains a byproduct acid salt, $\text{K}^+(\text{OAc}, \text{HOAc})^-$, which has been attributed to partial hydrolysis of Ac_2O and to a subsequent reaction of HOAc with K^+OAc^- . These two observations led us to repeat the synthesis of the "solvates" of Li, Na, K and NH_4 employing the reported¹ procedure and of the acid salts by a reaction of M^+OAc^- and HOAc in ethanol³. The observation was that for a given cation both reactions yielded the same product. Infrared spectral studies and hot stage microscopic examination of the products and the literature data⁴ (indexed in the Table) reveal that the products are invariably the acid salts even when procedure reported for the synthesis of the solvates¹ was adopted; 06° instead of 96° as the melting point for the Na-product in the original paper is understandably a lapse of proof reading.

Infrared spectra of the K^+ -products obtained from both the types of reactions, for example, are the same (see Figure). The ir spectra of all the products are ill defined which is indicative of the species being acid salts^{5,6}. An elaborated discussion provided by earlier authors¹ on the ir spectra,